

STRATEGIES AND METHODS FOR TEACHING ENGLISH TO YOUNG CHILDREN

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Abstract. This article discusses effective strategies and methods for teaching English to young children. It is known that young children have the ability to acquire language naturally and quickly. Therefore, interesting, game-based, interactive approaches to teaching them are more effective than traditional methods. This topic analyzes methods for teaching English to children, such as games, picture and video materials, listening comprehension, and language acquisition through physical movements. It also provides recommendations on how to organize a lesson, taking into account the age characteristics, psychological state, and attention span of children. The main goal of this work is to show creative, effective, and easy-to-learn methods for teaching English to children.

Keywords: Modern approaches to teaching, teaching methods, general physical response, scaffolding, feedback, visual aids, consistency, teaching teaching methods.

СТРАТЕГИИ И МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ ДЕТЕЙ МАЛЕНЬКОГО ВОЗРАСТА

Аннотация. В этой статье рассматриваются эффективные стратегии и методы обучения английскому языку маленьких детей. Известно, что маленькие дети обладают способностью усваивать язык естественно и быстро. Поэтому интересные, игровые, интерактивные подходы к их обучению более эффективны, чем традиционные методы. В этой теме анализируются методы обучения английскому языку детей, такие как игры, фото- и видеоматериалы, аудирование и усвоение языка посредством физических движений. Также даются рекомендации по организации урока с учетом возрастных особенностей, психологического состояния и концентрации внимания детей. Основная цель этой работы — показать креативные, эффективные и простые в освоении методы обучения английскому языку детей.

Ключевые слова: Современные подходы к обучению, методы обучения, общая физическая реакция, поддержка, обратная связь, наглядные пособия, последовательность, методы обучения преподаванию.

Introduction

Language plays a very important role in social life as a means of communication in human relations. English is the first foreign language for us, children learn English in the early stages of school. The main goal of teaching English in the early years of school education is to encourage young students to be prepared and behave in a way that will give them confidence in learning English in the higher stages of education. Some children are born to polyglot parents, so they have to learn two or three different languages. Some others learn a second or third language.

Nowadays, language learning is necessary for children who want to immigrate to other countries. Teaching techniques are the implementation of a teaching method at the level

in classroom exercises. To a certain extent, different methods may have similar techniques, although they should have different techniques. Based on the above different teaching methods, teachers can combine several teaching techniques in the classroom. It is important to observe the needs of the students, the purpose of the material and the situation in the classroom before using it. From this principle, the teacher can develop his own techniques, such as introducing songs and games, to make their learning interesting and natural. This article focuses on the main trends and problems in teaching English. By young language learners, we understand that learners fall within the age range of 6 to 14 years, although we are aware of the increasing number of programs for young children. The main part When choosing teaching strategies, the interests of young learners and their age should be taken into account. The more activities that can be used for the purpose of the lesson, the more interesting and exciting it can be. The techniques that teachers use when teaching English to young learners include singing songs, games, presentation practice and production, drills, demonstrations, storytelling, reading aloud, and dictation. The best teaching techniques are games, demonstrations, and presentations that teachers use to practice and produce. Build instruction around activities and physical movement. Linking language learning to physical activity helps children use and hear English as they make things, draw, do puzzles, label pictures, match words and pictures, play games, perform actions in response to instructions, and use their hands, eyes, and other movements to communicate with their ears. Teachers often use TPR activities (Tanguage-to-action, a method based on what is known as total physical response). Many listening activities for young children use this principle, such as having children listen to and respond to commands (e.g., “sit,” “turn around,” “touch nose”), listening and choosing a picture, listening and drawing a picture, or listening and numbering the sequence of actions in the picture.

Similarly, speaking activities with young learners include the use of songs, dialogues, rhymes, and concrete expressions that students can practice in a variety of situations.

If you have taken language lessons as a child and as an adult, you know how different the lessons can be. It is completely different to know how to teach English to these young learners.

Language is abstract and intangible by its very nature. In contrast, young learners are very literal and concrete. This makes it difficult to teach children the rules of grammar or syntax.

How do you teach a six-year-old the conditional? But don't worry. If you know the basic tactics for teaching English to children, your students will succeed. Even if they can't figure out the first conditional.

You should always remember to make the lesson fun, such as playing games and doing art, to keep the children's attention active, and never put too much pressure on them.

Literature review and methodology

Children speak the languages they hear. Thus, introducing English into your child's life will help him start using it. In the future, as the child grows up, his English speech will be repeated at an unconscious level and with the use of correct grammar. However, in order for the lessons to be truly effective and not overload the child, they must adhere to certain guidelines, which can be called the voluntary nature of the lessons. In no case should the child be forced to learn English.

Especially for a preschooler. If the lessons become a duty, they can quickly get bored, and later it may be difficult for the baby to learn the language. The main goal of parents and teachers is to instill interest in the language, and the game helps with this. Through the game, children learn the world and easily participate in this process, easily mastering important language skills.

An older child can be explained the benefits of English, but not in terms of future career advancement, although that is also useful, but rather in terms of the bonuses that will be available to him now, such as the ability to understand his favorite songs in English, the latest content, access to international gaming communities or other interest groups. Two key components of success in teaching children are a playful approach and consistency. It is known that children learn best through games, and it is important to have games that are age-appropriate for the students.

Although 3-year-olds and 8-year-olds may be different, you can still use the same games with higher-level language or vocabulary, such as increasing the difficulty. It is also very important to repeat the same games to help children remember what they have learned.

Creating variations of the same game and adding new things each time can keep things fresh, but it is important to repeat what children have already learned. Each task or game should include familiar elements, words, phrases, or actions, as well as some new ones. Avoid making games that are exactly the same or completely new activities because boredom can set in. Here are a few examples to further illustrate this theory. Learning about colors can be more fun than just showing color cards and naming colors. To make it more fun, give children paints or crayons and ask them to color using specific colors. As they begin to understand, you can increase the level by asking them to name the colors they are using. Involve students in creating resources that support reading. Students can draw pictures of characters they hear about in a story or create puppets that help them retell the story. They can color pictures of objects and characters in the stories. They can find pictures from magazines that relate to the lesson topic or theme and bring them to class.

Build lessons around themes. Lessons can be built around themes or topics such as animals, friends, food or family for very young students, and for older students, themes can be drawn from other classes and topics in the community, such as transport, village life, travel and famous people.

Theme-based lessons provide continuity throughout the activity and allow children to connect English learning to their lives.

Choose content that is familiar to children. Teaching can also be based on familiar content from the children's culture, such as stories and events, such as national holidays or cultural practices. Since students are familiar with these topics in their native language, it will be easier to relate to how they might be talked about

Discussion

Many teachers, citing the example of children speaking their native language without rules, say that they use it as a means of communication. And for the most part, they are right. But there are children who, even in their native language, make mistakes and correct themselves only when the rules are pointed out. The same thing happens to them when they learn the formula for constructing correct sentences in English. These analytical learners often excel in math and often ask "why." Rest assured, these learners demand logical answers. Returning to the topic of songs and rhymes, this can be a great way for students to learn new vocabulary and understand how to use it in context. However, for students with analytical thinking skills, additional explanations may be needed to fully understand the content of these materials.

It is important that songs and rhymes are relevant to the lesson and do not introduce more than 20% of the new vocabulary, otherwise it can become overwhelming for students. Also, do not forget to include books and songs in your lessons. Organizing a book corner in the classroom can be a great way to encourage students to read. If you use YouTube as a source of songs, unnecessary time can be spent during the lesson.

Using the optimal form of education that can work anytime, anywhere is an impractical approach. The learning process in the classroom and in separate classes will depend on the age of the children, their individual characteristics. In addition, a periodic change in the form of teaching will be a good approach. This will make lessons more interesting for young students.

The method of associations. The essence of this method is to establish chain connections between the meaning of English words in the child's language. The link can be words, imaginary images, feelings. It is advisable to use flashcards, bright pictures, sound effects, jokes, rhymes, schemes. Children should not just be given a word to remember (for example, the word pear), but also allow them to imagine the bulbous shape of this fruit, imagine how it lies in the palm of their hand, how hard or soft it is. what color and taste it has. Subsequently, a bright image will make it easier to find the necessary word in memory. Audiovisual method. Children read and memorize dialogues that they can use in everyday life. With their help, oral speech is well practiced.

Dialogues can be made more interesting by adapting them to each student and helping to conduct a conversation on a relevant topic with another student or teacher.

Results

A child does not have the same motivation to learn English as an adult. Until a certain age, a child does not think about the need to build a career or use a foreign language for work.

Therefore, it is important to interest the child in the process itself. If he is interested in the lessons, if they are interesting and not boring, the child himself will actively participate in the lessons. Therefore, there should be a comfort blanket for the child during the lesson. Some children easily stay in a group with other children and a teacher, while others need to be near one of the parents. This depends on the child's age and his character. If the lessons are held naturally for the child, he will begin to easily master the material. If you see that the child is resisting learning, you should not ignore him. Perhaps the methodology does not suit him, the teacher does not like him, or it is difficult for him. It is worth changing the approach to regain interest.

It makes no sense to burden children with rules, spelling and grammar until they are six years old, but it is good to learn new words together through songs, dances, games. The main thing is that the presentation of the material is consistent and that new knowledge is smoothly integrated into what the child is already familiar with. Teenagers can already learn the structure of the language. They use diagrams, illustrative examples of the use of a well-established phrase.

Learning a new skill also involves work. Sometimes it may seem that students do not show any visible results. At such moments, you need to support them and overcome the difficulties that arise without losing momentum with them. Perhaps you should experiment with techniques. It is important to remember that a reward or incentive at the end of this path is a great motivator.

Conclusion

Using these methods is effective in teaching English to young learners because they can help students have a good English learning experience. These strategies are suitable for teachers who make the learning process interesting and suitable for young learners. In addition, it is better for the teacher to create other creative teaching strategies (such as pair activities, group activities, and outdoor activities). Students will be more involved in the learning process as young learners.

Boring lessons should be skipped and interactive lessons should be established that both educate young learners and improve their language skills.

In order to reinforce what has been taught, teachers can choose activities rather than just questioning. One thing is for sure, even adults love to learn through games and activities. The study concluded that in order to diversify teaching methods in teaching English to young learners, especially in schools and kindergartens, teachers resort to singing, playing games, presentation practice and production, drill demonstration, storytelling, reading aloud, and writing dictation.

However, teachers encountered some problems in teaching, but they can solve the problems by stimulating and inviting students to play games, demonstration and presentation practice, and production.

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